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Title :

Doublet analysis of changes in electric potential induced by
delamination cracks in carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer laminates

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1. Introduction

Carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates are widely used as structural materials in aircraft and automobiles. CFRP laminates have a complicated structure that can promote distinctive damage modes, namely, delamination, fiber breakage, and matrix cracking [1]. As delamination cracks compromise the compressive strength, monitoring for cracks is necessary to guarantee the integrity of in-service CFRP components [2]. However, delamination cracks are generally externally invisible, making their detection difficult. Although ultrasonic testing is currently adopted in the inspection of delamination cracks, this method requires skilled experts and long inspection times for large structures [3]. Damage monitoring of CFRP laminates based on changes in electrical resistance has attracted attention as a self-sensing method [4]-[15]. This method, however, requires numerous data on the relationship between the damage and electrical resistance change, which are difficult to obtain using conventional numerical analysis methods in terms of computational cost. To reduce these inspection testing time and computational costs, a simple method for detecting delamination is highly sought.

A simple method to detect the location and size of delamination cracks based on the electrical properties of CFRP laminates has already been proposed for two-dimensional objects [16]-[18]. This method is based on the idea that delamination changes the electric potential distribution because when an electric voltage is applied, the current in the delamination area is prevented from flowing in the through-thickness direction of the laminate. Characteristics of the change in electric potential, therefore, enable us to estimate whether delamination cracks have appeared. Delamination cracks, which normally form two-dimensional defects in the in-plane direction of the laminate, are observed as delamination lines from the side. In this method, the doublet line is placed on the delamination line to imitate the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks. Here, the doublet line is a set of doublets directed in the through-thickness

direction to annihilate the electric current crossing the delamination line. However, this method can only be applied to two-dimensional objects that are composed of unidirectional and cross-ply laminates.

In the present study, a simple analysis method to estimate the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks was developed for three-dimensional objects. First, the matrix of three-dimensional doublets for the orthotropic electric field of CFRP laminates was newly defined. This new doublet-analysis method was then combined with the three-dimensional orthotropic potential function method, which has been previously validated as a simple analysis method for electric currents in CFRP laminates [19]–[22]. To demonstrate the validity of the proposed doublet-analysis method for electric potential change, the analysis results were compared with those obtained from the commonly used finite-element method (FEM).

2. Analysis method for electric potential change

2.1 Orthotropic electric potential function method

The simple method of analysis for the electric current is briefly explained here because the distribution of the electric current density in CFRP laminates is necessary for the doublet-analysis method. Here, unidirectional CFRP laminates are assumed to be homogeneously orthotropic electric conductive materials. A Cartesian three-dimensional coordinate system of the laminates is introduced: the fiber direction determines the x -axis with the transverse and through-thickness directions determining the y -axis and z -axis, respectively (Figure 1). Let the electric conductivity in each direction be defined as σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z . Using the orthotropic electric potential function ϕ , Ohm's law determines the electric current density in each direction: i_x , i_y , and i_z :

$$i_x = -\sigma_x \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}, \quad i_y = -\sigma_y \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}, \quad i_z = -\sigma_z \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}. \quad (1)$$

Conservation of charge results in the following equation:

$$\sigma_x \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \sigma_y \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \sigma_z \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0. \quad (2)$$

The following isotropic coordinate transformation

$$\xi = \frac{x}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}, \quad \eta = \frac{y}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}, \quad \zeta = \frac{z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}$$

is performed to transform equation (2) into Laplace's equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \zeta^2} = 0.$$

This equation is equivalent to that governing the potential describing the flow of a fluid. When the electric current flows in and out of a CFRP laminate, the input and output points of the current are regarded as source and sink points for the potential [19]. Locating the current input and output points at $(-a, 0, 0)$ and $(a, 0, T)$, respectively, the orthotropic electric potential function ϕ can be expressed as

$$\phi = \frac{I}{4\pi\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z}} \left\{ \frac{1}{\left(\frac{(x+a)^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} + \frac{y^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} + \frac{z^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \right)^{1/2}} - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{(x-a)^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} + \frac{y^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} + \frac{z^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \right)^{1/2}} \right\}. \quad (3)$$

Here, I is the applied electric current. The potential function for unidirectional CFRP laminates can be obtained by substituting the electric conductivities in the fiber direction, transverse direction, and through-thickness direction, σ_0 , σ_{90} , and σ_t , for σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z , respectively, in Equation (3). Solving Equation (1) gives the analytical solution for the electric current density in the laminate.

Let us consider the situation in which the electric current source and sink form lines (Figure 2). The red and blue lines in the figure correspond to the current source and sink lines respectively. This situation corresponds to the electrode arrangements employed as an

addressable conducting network for self-sensing of damage in a CFRP structure [15]. When the electric current source and sink are lines, each line can be considered as a set of source or sink points. The electric potential functions for the source at $(0, a_y, 0)$, denoted as $\phi_{\text{point_source}}$, and sink at $(a_x, 0, T)$, denoted as $\phi_{\text{point_sink}}$, can be expressed as

$$\phi_{\text{point_source}} = \frac{I}{4\pi(a_{2y} - a_{1y})\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z}} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{x^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} + \frac{(y-a_y)^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} + \frac{z^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}\right)^{1/2}}$$

$$\phi_{\text{point_sink}} = -\frac{I}{4\pi(a_{2x} - a_{1x})\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z}} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{(x-a_x)^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} + \frac{y^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} + \frac{(z-T)^2}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}\right)^{1/2}}.$$

By integrating these functions over the line $(a_{1y} \leq a_y \leq a_{2y})$ for the current source and $(a_{1x} \leq a_x \leq a_{2x})$ for the current sink, the following electric potential functions for the line source $\phi_{\text{line_source}}$ and line sink $\phi_{\text{line_sink}}$ can be obtained:

$$\phi_{\text{line}} = \int_{a_{1y}}^{a_{2y}} \phi_{\text{point_source}} da_y = \frac{I}{4\pi(a_{2y} - a_{1y})\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_z}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{2y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{y-a_{2y}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{1y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{y-a_{1y}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}}$$

$$\phi_{\text{line}} = \int_{a_{1x}}^{a_{2x}} \phi_{\text{point_sink}} da_x = -\frac{I}{4\pi(a_{2x} - a_{1x})\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_z}} \ln \frac{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{2x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{y^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-T)^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{x-a_{2x}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{1x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{y^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-T)^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{x-a_{1x}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}}.$$

The orthotropic electric potential function ϕ for a couple of source and sink lines described in Figure 2 can be expressed as

$$\phi = \frac{I}{4\pi\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_z}} \left\{ \frac{1}{(a_{2y} - a_{1y})} \ln \frac{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{2y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{y-a_{2y}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{1y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{y-a_{1y}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}} - \frac{1}{(a_{2x} - a_{1x})} \ln \frac{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{2x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{y^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-T)^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{x-a_{2x}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{1x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{y^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-T)^2}{\sigma_z}} - \frac{x-a_{1x}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}} \right\}.$$

If the size of the object is not large enough for the field to be treated as infinite, image charges are introduced with respect to the x , y , and z directions (Figure 3). The superposition of all solutions from all image charges ensures that the applied electric current flows through the

interior of the object considering boundary effects [16] [22].

2.2 Doublet analysis method

Delamination cracks are treated as zero-thickness planes that act as insulating material for the electric current flowing in the through-thickness direction. The electric current field of the laminates with delamination can be expressed as a superposition of two components: the field induced by the electric current source and sink and that induced by the sets of doublets introduced on the delamination surfaces to cancel out the electric current flow in the through-thickness direction. The details of this doublet analysis method are provided in the following description.

A three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system is introduced. When a doublet of strength μ directed along the z -direction is located at (x_0, y_0, d_z) , the electric potential, $\phi_{doublet}$, at the field point (x, y, z) due to the doublet can be expressed as [19] [23]

$$\phi_{doublet} = \frac{\mu(x_0, y_0, d_z)}{4\pi} \frac{\frac{z-d_z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_0)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{3}{2}}} . \quad (4)$$

Using Ohm's law, the electric current density, $i_{z, doublet}$, in the z -direction induced by the doublet at (x_0, y_0, d_z) can be expressed as

$$i_{z, doublet}(x, y, z) = \mu(x_0, y_0, d_z) \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}{4\pi} \frac{\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_0)^2}{\sigma_y} - 2\frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_0)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{5}{2}}} .$$

Doublets are introduced over the entire delamination area. The electric current density, $i_{z, crack}$, in the z -direction at point (x, y, z) induced by all the doublets can be calculated from the surface integral

$$i_{z,crack}(x, y, z) = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}{4\pi} \iint \mu(x_0, y_0, d_z) \frac{\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_0)^2}{\sigma_y} - 2\frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_0)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{5}{2}}} dx_0 dy_0 \quad (5)$$

The domain of integration is the surface area affected by delamination. Let us assume that the electric current source and sink are present in the field. As the electric current density on the delamination surface must be zero in the direction perpendicular to this surface, the equation for equilibrium

$$i_z(x, y, z) + i_{z,crack}(x, y, z) = 0 \quad (6)$$

must hold on the delamination surface. Here, i_z is the electric current density induced by the current source and sink. This situation is depicted in Figure 4. Equation (6) gives the strength of the doublet μ , which leads to the change in the electric potential caused by delamination given by Equation (4). Solving Equation (6), however, is difficult because Equation (5) is a hyper-singular integral equation evaluated over the delamination surface $z = d_z$. An approximation method to obtain μ is therefore proposed that avoids the singularity by considering the equilibrium equation at a point slightly shifted from the delamination surface, $z = d_z - \varepsilon$. Here, ε is a small nonzero value. To calculate μ , the delamination surface is divided into $N_x \times N_y$ grids (Figure 5). Throughout the grid, μ is assumed to be constant and equal to its value at the center of the grid (x_m, y_l, d_z) . This discretization technique enables Equation (6) to be written as

$$i_z(x, y, z) = -\frac{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}{4\pi} \sum_{m=1}^{N_x} \sum_{l=1}^{N_y} \mu_{ml} \frac{\frac{(x-x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} - 2\frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{5}{2}}} \Delta S \quad (7)$$

Here, μ_{ml} is defined as the value of the strength at (x_m, y_l, d_z) , and ΔS is the product $\Delta x \Delta y$. x_s and y_r are defined similarly to x_m, y_l , i.e., the x and y coordinates at the center of the grid. In addition, i_{sr} and F_{srml} are defined as

$$i_{sr} = i_z(x_s, y_r, d_z - \varepsilon) = -\frac{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}{4\pi} \sum_{m=1}^{N_x} \sum_{l=1}^{N_y} \mu_{ml} \frac{\frac{(x_s - x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y_r - y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} - 2\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_z}}{\left\{ \frac{(x_s - x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y_r - y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{5}{2}}} \Delta S \quad (8)$$

$$F_{srml} = -\frac{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}{4\pi} \frac{\frac{(x_s - x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y_r - y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} - 2\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_z}}{\left\{ \frac{(x_s - x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y_r - y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{5}{2}}} \Delta S \quad (9)$$

Using i_{sr} and F_{srml} , Equation (7) can be written as

$$i_{sr} = F_{srml} \mu_{ml},$$

where i_{sr} and μ_{ml} are second-order tensors and F_{srml} is a fourth-order tensor. To obtain each component of μ_{ml} , $[i]$, $[F]$, and $[\mu]$ are defined as matrices:

$$[i] = \begin{bmatrix} i_{11} & \cdots & i_{N_x 1} & i_{12} & \cdots & i_{N_x 2} & \cdots & i_{1N_y} & \cdots & i_{N_x N_y} \end{bmatrix}^T$$

$$[F] = \begin{bmatrix} F_{1111} & \cdots & F_{11N_x 1} & F_{1112} & \cdots & F_{11N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{111N_y} & \cdots & F_{11N_x N_y} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ F_{N_x 111} & \cdots & F_{N_x 1N_x 1} & F_{N_x 112} & \cdots & F_{N_x 1N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{N_x 11N_y} & \cdots & F_{N_x 1N_x N_y} \\ F_{1211} & \cdots & F_{12N_x 1} & F_{1212} & \cdots & F_{12N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{121N_y} & \cdots & F_{12N_x N_y} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ F_{N_x 211} & \cdots & F_{N_x 2N_x 1} & F_{N_x 212} & \cdots & F_{N_x 2N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{N_x 21N_y} & \cdots & F_{N_x 2N_x N_y} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ F_{1N_y 11} & \cdots & F_{1N_y N_x 1} & F_{1N_y 12} & \cdots & F_{1N_y N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{1N_y 1N_y} & \cdots & F_{1N_y N_x N_y} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ F_{N_x N_y 11} & \cdots & F_{N_x N_y N_x 1} & F_{N_x N_y 12} & \cdots & F_{N_x N_y N_x 2} & \cdots & F_{N_x N_y 1N_y} & \cdots & F_{N_x N_y N_x N_y} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$[\mu] = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{11} & \cdots & \mu_{N_x 1} & \mu_{12} & \cdots & \mu_{N_x 2} & \cdots & \mu_{1N_y} & \cdots & \mu_{N_x N_y} \end{bmatrix}^T.$$

Their relationship is expressible as

$$[i] = [F][\mu]. \quad (10)$$

Multiplying both sides of Equation (10) from the left with the inverse matrix of $[F]$, $[F]^{-1}$, one obtains

$$[\mu] = [F]^{-1} [i].$$

Using each component of $[\mu]$ gives the change in electric potential induced by each doublet introduced on the delamination surface. This change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks can be obtained from the integrals of all contributions from the entire set of doublets. The change in electric potential at (x, y, z) , ϕ_{crack} , is therefore calculated using

Equation (4) and the values obtained for μ_{ml} :

$$\phi_{crack}(x, y, z) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{m=1}^{N_x} \sum_{l=1}^{N_y} \mu_{ml} \frac{\frac{z-d_z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{(z-d_z)^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{3}{2}}} \Delta S$$

To obtain an accurate solution, the contribution from the sets of image charge doublets surrounding the object must also be superposed. Calculating the strengths of all doublets, however, is a time-consuming process. The doublet-analysis method has the advantage of providing a less intensive calculation compared with commonly used numerical methods such as FEM. In the present study, the set of doublets from only one image charge adjacent to the object in the through-thickness direction is superposed to effect a low calculation cost. Considering this image charge, the change in the electric potential ΔV on the top surface ($x, y, 0$) induced by delamination cracks can be expressed as

$$\Delta V = 2\phi_{crack}(x, y, 0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{m=1}^{N_x} \sum_{l=1}^{N_y} \mu_{ml} \frac{\frac{d_z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}}{\left\{ \frac{(x-x_m)^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-y_l)^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{d_z^2}{\sigma_z} \right\}^{\frac{3}{2}}} \Delta S$$

3. Comparison of results and discussion

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in calculating the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks, the analysis results are compared with those of FEM. For the FEM analysis, the commercially available software ANSYS ver. 16.2 was used. For the comparison, unidirectional CFRP laminates with a couple of source and sink points were configured as the analysis model. The laminates with a couple of source and sink lines were also analyzed, and their results are discussed below.

3.1 Analytical model and condition

Two different models were first studied: model 1 had one large delamination, and model 2

had two small delaminations. The details of the model dimensions are provided in Figure 6. The fiber was directed along the x -direction. The input electric current I was set to 1 A, and the distance between the current input/output point and origin a was set to 10 mm. The important parameters for electrical analysis are the ratios of electrical conductivity for each direction; the electric conductivities for the three directions were set to $\sigma_x = 1$ S/m, $\sigma_y = 0.1$ S/m, and $\sigma_z = 0.01$ S/m. The dimensions of the delamination were set to 6 mm \times 6 mm for model 1 and 4 mm \times 4 mm for model 2. The centers of the delaminations were located at $(d_x, d_y, d_z) = (-5, 3, 0.1)$ for model 1 and at $(-10, 0, 0.4)$ and $(2, 0, 0.1)$ for model 2. For the FEM analysis, rectangular elements with 20 nodes having dimensions of 0.5 mm \times 0.5 mm \times 0.025 mm were adopted. The size of elements was decided by checking that the smaller elements do not change the analysis results. Input current was set to 1A and applied to the point at $(-10, 0, 0)$, and the electric voltage of grounding point at $(10, 0, 1)$ was set to 0V. The nodes on the delamination surface were doubly defined and not merged, hence blocking any electrical conduction in the through-thickness direction. The change of the electric potential induced by delamination cracks were calculated by subtracting the calculated potential of sound laminate from that of laminate with delamination cracks. In the doublet-analysis method, the short distance ε in Equations (8) and (9) was set to 0.01 mm to avoid the singularity in the equilibrium equation. Discretization was performed by dividing the delamination area into 21 \times 21 grids ($N_x = N_y = 21$) for model 1 and 14 \times 14 grids ($N_x = N_y = 14$) for model 2. The change in electric potential on the top surface, $z = 0$, was calculated using the doublet-analysis method and FEM and compared.

Two different models with lines of current input and output with delamination were then studied, model 3 and model 4. The details of the model dimensions are provided in Figure 7. For the FEM analysis, uniformly distributed electric current was applied to the source and sink lines. The total current was set to 1A. In the doublet-analysis method, the short distance ε in

Equations (8) and (9) was set to 0.011 mm. Discretization was performed by dividing the delamination area into 21×21 grids ($N_x = N_y = 21$) for model 3 and 14×14 grids ($N_x = N_y = 14$) for model 4. The other analytical conditions were the same as those used in the previous models. The effect of the line source and sink on the delamination detection compared with that of the point source and sink is discussed.

3.2 Comparison with FEM analysis and discussion

The contour diagrams in Figure 8 display the analysis results for the change in electric potential on the top surface. The color scale indicates the magnitude of change of the electric potential, with red representing the largest change and blue representing the smallest change. Since the amount of the current flow disturbed by delamination cracks depends on the location and dimensions of delaminations, the largest values of the change in electric potential are different for two models. The diagrams demonstrate the good agreement of the doublet-analysis and FEM method results. To see the finer details, the x -axis profiles for the change in electric potential at $y = z = 0$ are presented in Figure 9. The resulting curves strongly overlap, demonstrating the effectiveness of the doublet-analysis method in calculating the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks.

The contour diagrams in Figure 10 display the analysis results for the change in electric potential on the top surface for line source and sink models. The largest values of the change in potential for two models are different for the same reason of the previous models. The figures demonstrate the good agreement of the doublet-analysis and FEM methods. The x -axis profiles for the change in electric potential at $y = z = 0$ are presented in Figure 11. The good agreement of the models is clearly observed for each curve, demonstrating the effectiveness of the doublet-analysis method even for a line source and sink.

The electrical orthotropy of CFRP laminates allows a small amount of electric current from

a point source to spread in the width (y) direction, which leads to difficulty in detecting delamination away from the x -axis. The area of large potential change is represented by the red stretch in the y -direction in the line source and sink models (Figure 10) compared with the results for the point source and sink models (Figure 8). This result indicates that the line source and sink enable the electric current to effectively spread in the width direction, making the electric potential change sensitive to delamination away from the x -axis.

In terms of calculation time, the doublet-analysis method took 4 s, whereas the FEM method took 386 s using the same computer. The doublet-analysis method therefore demonstrates great efficacy and efficiency compared with the FEM method, even though the calculated results were almost the same.

In this study, delamination cracks located near the top surface were dealt with, and those effects on the potential change were successfully analyzed. Typical delamination cracks are created near on both top and bottom surfaces by impact. The magnitude of the change on the surface depends on the distance between the delamination and the surface. The potential change on the top surface induced by delamination located near the bottom can be calculated by the doublet-analysis method in the same way, although the calculated values are tiny. When delamination cracks form in several layers, potential change can be obtained by superposition of all the contributions from three-dimensional doublets corresponding to the delaminations, as long as the effect of doublets on other doublets is negligible.

The effectiveness of the doublet-analysis method for the calculation of electric potential change induced by delamination cracks with a reduction of calculation time was thus demonstrated. In the doublet-analysis method, the entire analytical model does not need to be divided into small elements to calculate the change in potential, as required in the FEM approach. The advantage of the proposed method, therefore, would be more pronounced in addressing a larger-scale model. The doublet-analysis method may enable the calculation of the

potential difference caused by delamination cracks for laminates with angled plies, which remains difficult using conventional FEM because of the high computational cost. The investigation of this possibility will be the subject of our future work.

4. Conclusions

To calculate the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks, three-dimensional doublets were introduced in modeling the delamination surface. An approximation method to determine the strength of the doublet was developed in combination with the three-dimensional orthotropic potential function method. Through comparisons with FEM results, the effectiveness of the doublet-analysis method in calculating the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks was demonstrated; in addition, this new method resulted in low calculation costs. Finally, comparison of a point source and sink model and a line source and sink model demonstrated the improved effectiveness of the line model in detecting delamination cracks over a wide range.

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References

- [1] Mallick PK, FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES: Materials, Manufacturing and

Design, Third Edition, CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group, 2007

- [2] Züleyha A and Mustafa Ş, Buckling behavior and compressive failure of composite laminates containing multiple large delaminations, *Composite Structures* 2009;89(3):382-390.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2008.08.011>
- [3] Wong BS, Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) of composites: detecting delamination defects using mechanical impedance, ultrasonic and infrared thermographic techniques, *Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) of Polymer Matrix Composites* 2013:279-305
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1533/9780857093554.2.279>
- [4] Schulte K and Baron Ch, Load and Failure Analyses of CFRP Laminates by Means of Electrical Resistively Measurements, *Composites Science and Technology* 1989;36(1):63-76.
- [5] Muto N, Yanagida H, Nakatsuji T, Sugita M and Ohtsuka Y, Preventing Fatal Fractures in Carbon-Fibre-Glass-Fibre-Reinforced Plastic Composites by Monitoring Change in Electrical Resistance, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 1993;76(4):875-879.
- [6] Chen PW and Chung DDL, Carbon Fiber Reinforced Concrete for Smart Structures Capable of Non-Destructive Flaw Detection, *Smart Materials and Structures* 1993;2:22-30.
- [7] Kaddour AS, Al-Salehi FA and Al-Hassani STS, Electrical Resistance Measurement Technique for Detecting Failure in CFRP Materials at High Strain Rate, *Composite Science and Technology* 1994;51(3):377-385.
- [8] Irving PE and Thiagarajan C, Fatigue Damage Characterization in Carbon Fibre Composite Materials using an Electric Potential Technique, *Smart Materials and Structures* 1998;7(4):456-466.
- [9] Abry JC, Bochart S, Chateauminois A, Salvia M and Giraud G, In situ detection of damage in CFRP laminates by electric resistance measurements, *Composites Science and Technology* 1999;59(6):925-935.
- [10] Seo DC and Lee JJ, Damage Detection of CFRP Laminates using Electrical Resistance

Measurement and Neural Network, *Composite Structures* 1999;47(1-4):525-530.

[11] Todoroki A, Tanaka M and Shimamura Y, Measurement of orthotropic electric conductance of CFRP laminates and analysis of the effect on delamination monitoring with an electric resistance change method, *Composites Science and Technology* 2002;62(5):619-628.

[12] Todoroki A and Tanaka Y, Delamination identification of cross-ply graphite/epoxy composite beams using electric resistance change method, *Composites Science and Technology* 2002;62(5):629-639.

[13] Ogi K and Takao Y, Characterization of piezoresistance behavior in a CFRP unidirectional laminate, *Composites Science and Technology* 2005;65(2):231-239.

[14] Selvakumaran L and Lubineau G, Electrical behaviour of laminated composites with intralaminar degradation: a comprehensive micro-meso homogenization procedure, *Composite Structures* 2014;109:178-188.

[15] Takahashi K, Park J and Hahn T, An addressable conducting network for autonomic structural health management of composite structures, *Smart Materials and Structures* 2010;19(10):1050-60.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/19/10/105023>

[16] Todoroki A and Arai M, Simple electric-voltage-change-analysis method for delamination of thin CFRP laminates using anisotropic electric potential function, *Advanced Composite Materials* 2014;23(3):261-273.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09243046.2013.851357>

[17] Todoroki A, New analytical method for electric current and multiple delamination cracks for thin CFRP cross-ply laminates using equivalent electric conductance, *Advanced Composite Materials* 2016;25(1):87-101.

[18] Matsuzaki R, Yamamoto K and Todoroki A, Crack Swarm Inspection for Estimation of Crack Location in Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics: A Numerical Study, *Composite*

Structures 2017;160(15):36-42.

[19] Todoroki A, Electric Current Analysis of CFRP using Perfect Fluid Potential Flow. Transactions of the Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences 2012;55(3):183-190.

[20] Todoroki A, Electric Current Analysis for Thick Laminated CFRP Composites, Transactions of the Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences 2012;55(4):237-243.

[21] Yamane T, Todoroki A, Fujita H, Kawashima A and Sekine N, Electric current distribution of carbon fiber reinforced polymer beam: analysis and experimental measurements, Advanced Composite Materials 2016;25(6):497-513.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09243046.2015.1126665>

[22] Yamane T, and Todoroki A, Analysis of electric current density in carbon fiber reinforced plastic laminated plates with angled plies, Composite Structures 2017;166(5):268-276.

[23] Katz J. and Plotkin A, Low-Speed Aerodynamics, 2nd edition, New York (NY): Cambridge University Press; 2011.

Figures

Fig. 1 Unidirectional CFRP laminate with electric current source and sink points.

Fig. 2 Unidirectional CFRP laminate with electric current source and sink lines signified by red and blue respectively.

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of the method of image charges.

Fig. 4 Principle of superposition of doublets on the delamination surface.

Fig. 5 Grid divisions of delamination surface for the surface integral calculation.

Fig. 6 Schematic representations of two different types of analytical models with delamination cracks with point

source and sink.

Fig. 7 Schematic representations of two different types of analytical models with delamination cracks with line source and sink.

Fig. 8 Contour diagrams of calculated results for the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks on the top surface for point source and sink models.

Fig. 9 Detailed profile of the change in electric potential along the x -axis for the two models with point source and sink. The solid lines represent the results of the doublet-analysis method, and the square symbols represent the FEM results.

Fig. 10 Contour diagrams of calculated results for the change in electric potential induced by delamination cracks on the top surface for line source and sink models.

Fig. 11 Detailed profile of the change in electric potential along with the x -axis for the two models with line source and sink. The solid lines represent the results of the doublet-analysis method, and the square symbols represent the FEM results.